

IN-PROCESS MONITORING OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES USING ACOUSTIC EMISSION

S. Canumalla, B. R. Tittmann, R. N. Pangborn, J. C. Conway, Jr. and R. B. Bhagat

Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics

The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16802, USA

ABSTRACT

Discontinuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) offer attractive properties for structural and thermal management applications if they are free from processing flaws. An efficient and cost effective approach to optimizing MMC fabrication procedure is to use in-process sensing techniques to study the effect of changing the process variables on the quality of the composites. In this study, acoustic emission (AE) is used to monitor the high pressure infiltration process in which A356 aluminum alloy is infiltrated into aluminosilicate discontinuous fiber preforms. After optimizing the position and frequency of the AE resonant transducers, acoustic signatures characteristic of incomplete infiltration and metal solidification are isolated and identified by examining the energy distribution of various events.

Keywords : Metal matrix composites, Process Monitoring, Acoustic Emission, High Pressure Infiltration Casting

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs), especially aluminum composites, represent promising alternatives to conventional alloys in engine applications because they are lighter, stronger, stiffer, and offer higher operating temperature, better wear resistance, and enhanced dimensional stability¹. These superior material properties translate into tangible benefits, such as more reliable and efficient engines that are capable of operating at higher temperatures. However, the drawbacks of using these advanced composites are the increased fabrication cost, difficulty in assessing the reliability, and lack of a sufficiently comprehensive design database.

With the advent of low cost ceramic fibers, renewed effort has been directed towards the development of fabrication techniques to make mass production economically attractive. Various manufacturing techniques are used in the production of MMCs for cost sensitive applications, such as in the automotive industry. Of these, the technique of infiltrating molten metal into fiber preforms is considered attractive as it offers the potential for near net shape forming². A variation of the infiltration technique, with high infiltration pressures, is particularly suitable as it enables the fabrication of composites that have a small grain size, exhibit intimate contact between the fibers and matrix, and are relatively free from porosity³. The infiltration kinetics and various mechanical properties of composites made by this process have been studied by many researchers^{4, 5}. Marked improvements were found in such properties as high temperature strength, stiffness, wear resistance and hardness, as compared to matrix materials⁶. These properties could be further improved by minimizing processing flaws and enhancing the reliability of processing.

Although the infiltration process is attractive from both commercial application and composite performance aspects, various flaws may develop in the composite during the processing. Because ceramic fibers are not readily wetted by molten aluminum⁴, high pressure is employed to overcome the surface tension opposing the infiltration of the melt. This also minimizes interfacial reaction due to rapid solidification and cooling of the composite, and reduces shrinkage cavities and porosity that may be caused by the entrapment of gas⁷. Conversely, because of the high pressure, the preform may be compressed or crushed if the molten alloy solidifies prematurely near the cold die walls or the pressure required to infiltrate the preform is greater than its compressive strength⁸. Incomplete infiltration may be a result of fiber clumping that locally restricts the flow of the melt around the individual fibers and porosity may be caused by inadequate applied pressures or dissolved gases in the molten alloy.

Such processing flaws could be avoided by optimizing the process parameters such as the pressure exerted during infiltration, viscosity of the molten metal, volume fraction and arrangement of fibers, and temperature of molten metal, preform and die. One approach to the process optimization is the use of rigorous, analytical models of the infiltration process to predict the optimum processing parameters. Various models that have been proposed by Clyne and Mason⁴, Mortensen et al.⁵, and Fukunaga⁹, among others, are useful when the fiber architecture is simple and the process is carried out under controlled laboratory conditions. A different approach to the process optimization is to nondestructively monitor the processing. This study makes use of acoustic emission (AE) which is an in situ, nondestructive sensing technique to detect processing abnormalities.

Acoustic emission (AE) is capable of providing information on microstructural evolution and on processing defects, such as matrix micro-cracking in carbon-carbon pyrolysis¹⁰. The acousto-elastic signals carry information about the entire process volume without interfering with the process. Although the concept is relatively straightforward, process monitoring with AE poses practical problems, such as the background noise, high temperatures and pressures encountered in the processing environment. Therefore, sophisticated transducers and signal processing techniques are needed to capture the pertinent acousto-elastic signals in the presence of background noise. AE has been used mainly for the investigation of the micromechanisms of deformation and fracture during mechanical testing^{11,12,13}, and for the detection of flaws in stressed structures¹⁴. A more recent trend has been to apply AE analysis for in-process monitoring, based on the observation that microstructural changes and flaws induced by processing emit "characteristic" acoustic emission^{11,15}. However, the usefulness of AE as a process monitoring tool is dependent on the detectability of acoustic signals emitted as a result of the material's response during fabrication¹⁶.

The problem at hand can be generically classified as a solidification process with associated fiber fracture events. AE can be generated by processing flaws such as preform crushing and porosity, and events such as solidification, in addition to the background noise. Although acoustic emission has been applied for the in-process monitoring of carbon-carbon pyrolysis¹¹ and spot welding¹⁶, it has not been employed to investigate MMC fabrication processes.

2. THE INFILTRATION PROCESS

The preform used in this study, shown in Figure 1, is a rigid, porous solid consisting of an interconnected network of low-cost alumino-silicate fibers (KAOWOOL®) with silica binder added for dimensional stability (obtained from Thermal Ceramics Company, Atlanta, Georgia, USA). These fibers tend to form a random mat which imparts transversely isotropic properties to the composite.

The High Pressure Infiltration Casting (HiPIC) apparatus, shown in Figure 2, consists of a cylindrical die and punch, and a hydraulic ram to drive the punch into the die cavity. A ram speed of 10 mm/s was used in the infiltration experiments. An aluminum alloy A356, with

7% Si and 0.3% Mg was selected because of its superior castability. The required amount of alloy was weighed, placed in a crucible and heated in a furnace at 1000 °C for 20 to 30 minutes, while the preform was separately preheated to the same temperature for the same amount of time. Then, the preform was placed in the die such that it was isolated from the die walls to minimize heat loss prior to infiltration. The molten alloy was then poured in, the punch was inserted into the die cavity, and a high pressure (100 MPa) was applied for approximately 60 seconds.

In contrast to the method followed by Dinwoodie et al.⁶, Bader et al.⁸, and Rasmussen et al.¹⁷, where the die was preheated to a temperature exceeding 250° C, the use of a room temperature die is advantageous because it results in shorter turn-around times and minimal chemical reaction between the fiber and matrix. However, the use of a room temperature die may also promote preform crushing, because the process variable “window” over which infiltration is possible, is narrower.

Figure 1 Scanning electron micrograph of a 8% V_f fiber preform showing the random fiber architecture

3 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

A data acquisition system (LOCAN-AT, Physical Acoustics Corporation) and transducers in the frequency range 100-300 kHz and 400-600 kHz were used to collect AE data. In initial experiments, the ambient noise created problems during data acquisition because the dead time associated with the high energy background noise was long enough to freeze the instrumentation. Therefore, until the background noise could be separated from the pertinent AE, low gain and high threshold were used to prevent machine shutdown. Acoustic emission transducers were attached to the die, as shown in Figure 2, and an ultrasonic jelly was used to achieve acoustic coupling. The transducer arrangement enabled simultaneous optimization of the frequency and location of transducer.

The test matrix, shown in Table 1, consists of two sets of experiments:

- Experiments A, B and C were conducted to identify the optimum frequency that would minimize contribution from machine noise and maximize AE from preform crushing and metal solidification. One 100-300 kHz transducer and two 400-600 kHz transducers were employed simultaneously to collect AE, with gain and threshold settings of 40 dB and 55 dB, respectively, as follows:

Table 1. Test matrix showing the variables in the different experiments conducted

Experiment	Variables	Transducers †	Expected Result	Data Plot
A	Machine Noise only	I,II,III	Frequency content of machine noise	Figure 4
B	Machine Noise + Preform Crushing	I, II, III	Frequency window of preform crushing	Figure 5
C	Machine Noise + Metal Solidification	I, II, III	Frequency window of metal solidification	Figure 6
D	Crushing of 20 % Vf <u>room temperature preform</u> + metal solidification + <i>ambient noise</i> §	III	Signature of Preform Crushing when metal solidifies before infiltration	Figure 7
E	Crushing of 8 % Vf <u>room temperature preform</u> + metal solidification + <i>ambient noise</i> §	III	Signature of Preform Crushing when metal solidifies before infiltration	Figure 7
F	Complete infiltration of a 20 %Vf preheated preform + metal + <i>ambient noise</i> §	III	Signature of Complete Infiltration -> infiltration + metal solidification	Figure 7
G	Complete infiltration of a 8 %Vf preheated preform + metal + <i>ambient noise</i> §	III	Signature of Complete Infiltration -> infiltration + metal solidification	Figure 7
H	Metal Solidification + <i>ambient noise</i> §	III	Signature of Metal Solidification excluding infiltration events	Figure 7

† - The transducer I, II and III are as follows, and shown schematically in Figure 1:

I - 400 - 600 kHz transducer attached to the side of the die

II - 100 - 300 kHz transducer attached to the side of the die

III - 400 -600 kHz transducer attached to base of the die

§ - The ambient noise denotes the machine noise after a significant portion has been eliminated by using transducer III

Experiment A - AE from ambient noise, such as mechanical noise from the press and ram insertion, while operating the hydraulic press without actually using the preform or molten metal

Figure 2. Schematic of the die used for the infiltration, the location of the transducers and the instrumentation employed.

Experiment B - AE from preform crushing along with the ambient noise while performing experiment "A", but this time with the preform included

Experiment C - AE from the metal solidification along with ambient noise collected by performing experiment "A", along with molten metal poured into the die, but without any preform

- AE data from experiments D, E, F, G and H were collected with a 400-600 kHz transducer to study complete infiltration and preform crushing and characterize the acoustic signature corresponding to metal solidification and preform crushing. A gain of 60 dB and a threshold of 20 dB were employed to render the data acquisition system more sensitive to AE signals resulting from preform crushing than from other sources. Since most of the noise was filtered out by using the 400-600 kHz transducer, the contribution from the background noise was expected to be minimal in spite of the higher gain used. The three events of metal solidification, complete infiltration, and incomplete infiltration were simulated, respectively, by using just the molten alloy, molten alloy and preheated preform, and a cold preform.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among the various signal measurement parameters frequently used to describe a burst type acoustic signal (Figure 3), energy (Measured Area under the Rectified Signal Envelope or MARSE) is a measure of both amplitude and duration, and is relatively less dependent on threshold settings as compared to counts, hits or duration. The energy of a burst type signal, which is obtained by electronic integration, has the units of volt-second. The energy of the AE hits collected by the three transducers is plotted as a function of time for the case of machine noise only (A) in Figure 4. A time of zero on this plot corresponds to the beginning of data acquisition, and therefore, is an arbitrary datum. There are three distinct peaks at 12, 24 and 50 seconds, approximately. These correspond to the major events during the processing: the first of these peaks is due to the starting of the hydraulic machinery, the second is due to the ram coming down on the punch, and the last peak is due to the reversal of the ram. The period between the second and third peaks is the time for which pressure is applied on the punch where infiltration, preform crushing and solidification are expected to occur. AE from the three channels was collected simultaneously, under similar threshold and gain settings. In particular, the figure shows that the 100-300 kHz transducer picked up the most hits, whereas the other two registered significantly fewer hits. This shows that the frequency of the ambient noise consisted of acoustic emissions having frequencies less than 300 kHz.

The response of the preform crushing together with machine noise was then obtained by crushing a preform in the die cavity (B). Again, the AE data were collected with all three transducers simultaneously. Figure 5 shows the energy of the AE hits plotted as a function of the time elapsed. As in the previous case, the peaks in AE activity correspond to the machine startup, contact of the ram and punch, and the ram being reversed; and the zero on the time scale corresponds to the beginning of data acquisition. In this case, it is seen that the 100-300 kHz transducer registers very little activity between the two peaks, whereas the 400-600 kHz transducer at the base picks up more AE than a similar transducer placed at the side of the die. This suggests that the base transducer was more sensitive to the preform crushing yet is less sensitive to the ambient noise. This is consistent with the observation that the ambient noise is generated closer to the top of the die, and in the die design, the base of the die was not in complete contact with the top part. Both of these factors probably result in the base transducer being isolated from the ambient noise more effectively than the transducer at the side of the die. The response of the metal solidification along with the ambient noise (Figure 6) indicates that metal solidification consists chiefly of low energy events in the 400-600 kHz range. The results also suggest that the metal solidification was complete within 20-25 seconds after pressure was applied, because the high frequency events cease after about 35 seconds on the time scale and lower frequency, high energy events dominate the later part of the process. Once it was established that the preform crushing and metal solidification occurred at frequencies greater than 300 kHz, the base of the die was modified to accommodate a 400-600 kHz transducer.

Experiments (D, E, F, G and H) were conducted using the 400-600 kHz transducer located at the base of the die. Five experiments were conducted to identify the signatures corresponding to preform crushing, complete infiltration and metal solidification. The energy spectrum of the data collected from the 5 different experiments was examined by plotting the number of hits (or events) per energy bin, as shown in Figure 7. It is seen that the metal solidification and complete infiltration achieve the maximum number of events in the bin with energy of 1.5 volt-sec, whereas both the preform crushing data sets exhibit the largest number of events in the energy bin with energy of 5.5 volt-sec. Also the latter data sets (preform crushing along with metal solidification) have some lower energy components also due to the contribution of the solidifying metal. The number of events with energy 5.5 volt-sec is more than twice as large for the 20% as for the 8% preform crushing. This must be expected because the denser preform has more fibers that could contribute to the total AE activity.

Figure 3. Schematic of an burst type acoustic emission hit and energy (MARSE) .

Figure 4 Energy vs. time plot of the machine noise experiment (A) showing that the number, and energy of hits recorded by the 400-600kHz transducers to be minimal

Figure 5. Energy vs. time plot of the preform crushing experiment (B) showing the energy of hits recorded by the three transducers as a function of time (in seconds)

Figure 6 Energy vs. time plot of the metal solidification experiment (C) showing that the number, and energy of hits recorded by the 400-600 kHz transducers to be maximum until solidification has occurred, and then increase in hits in 100-300 kHz transducer.

Figure 7 The energy content of the events collected by the 400-600 kHz transducer illustrating the difference in the signature between the preform crushing and good infiltration.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The various events in the infiltration process have been identified from plots of AE hit rate as a function of processing time. With the use of three transducers, the optimum location of the transducers and the frequency response of the ambient noise, preform crushing and metal solidification were identified. By judicious selection of the frequency window, the background noise could be partially suppressed. Preform crushing seemed to generate hits with higher energy content as compared to metal solidification. In these experiments, metal solidification could not be distinguished from complete infiltration-solidification. It may be possible to discern such subtle differences by using more sensitive instrumentation and examining the spectral content of AE signals. The applicability of AE as a non-intrusive, in-situ technique to detect gross preform crushing in the HiPIC process was investigated and the results are encouraging. A more sophisticated, computer controlled data acquisition scheme that is capable of collecting hits in a narrow energy, frequency or amplitude window is suggested for better signal resolution and background suppression.

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